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Impact of Media and Marketing on Sustainable Development of Traditional Craft Villages in Vietnam

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Abstract:

The goal of the paper is to analyze the media and marketing practices in traditional craft villages. This assessment aims to examine the extend of influence of these practices on the sustainability of traditional craft villages. From there, analyses and recommendations are made to preserve traditional crafts.

Keywords: media, marketing, sustainable development, traditional craft villages, Vietnam

1. Introduction

An integral element of cultural heritage, traditional craft villages embody the century-long traditions of craftsmanship through generations. Not only does traditional craft play a pivotal role in culture but it is also regarded as a crucial tool for economic growth, and job creation (Bellver, 2023), which supports sustainable development as a whole. However, craft villages have encountered various opportunities and challenges in the growing globalization and digital revolution of the 21st century. The growing popularity of mass-produced products and changes in preferences pose threats to these craft villages.

In the growing modernization and globalization, marketing tools and media platforms play an integral role in shaping the image of traditional crafts and refining consumer perceptions of these craft villages. Considering the case in Vietnam, the impact of media and marketing on craft villages is profound. These forces reshape multiple aspects of traditional craftsmanship, ranging from brand visibility to market engagement, fostering economic growth while still preserving cultural heritage.

This research aims to analyze the impacts of the interactions between media, marketing, and traditional crafts. Through this analysis, we seek to assess the extend of influence that media and marketing have on the sustainable development of traditional craft villages.

The structure of the article in addition to the introduction includes: Literature Rerview, The current situation of some traditional villages in Vietnam, Interviews Results and Conclusion.

2. Literature review

2.1. Media and Marketing

Media are communication forms which help people access necessary information in the social world. (Couldry and Van Dijick, 2015) Media can be divided into two main types: mass media and social media.

According to Lee in 2014, mass media are tools that assist humans in the circulation of information, experience and entertainment. These tools can occur in both printed forms such as books, newspapers and magazines, or electronic forms like television, and radio. A notable feature of mass media is the “unidirectional flow of homogenous messages” from the conveyor to the audience, with little or no feedback. While the communicator is not aware if their messages reach the audience and the underlying meanings are understood, the audience can not generate immediate or customized responses to serve their purposes of communication. Audience can choose to receive the messages, but cannot interfere to shape the content or change the flow of communication. (Lee, 2014)

On the other hand, social media take the form of online tools that facilitate interactions, collaborations and the sharing of content (Richter & Koch, 2007). These can range from weblogs, and wikis, to podcasts and social bookmarking. As social media rocketed in popularity, increasingly more people are joining these platforms for communication, advertising and marketing. The advent of social media has prompted crucial transformations in the media landscape, enabling new marketing practices with reduced expense and effort. (Kim and Ko, 2012)

About marketing definition, according to the American Marketing Association, as cited by Grönroos in 2006, marketing involves “an organizational function and a set of processes” aiming to generate, communicate, and provide value to customers, while also maintaining relationships with customers, thus benefiting both the organization and its stakeholders. Grönroos, C. (2006).

Marketing is a process that seemingly remains inside the organization, not depending on factors that affect decision-making procedures. The process is the foundation of marketing, while structural aspects facilitate that process. (Grönroos, C. (2006).

Originating as a scientific discipline, marketing primarily focused on formulating and mathematizing the concept. Differentiation started to occur based on the original concept, with two main perspectives: managerial marketing and behavioural marketing. Managerial marketing concentrates on suppliers, analyzing the effective method for companies to handle the market such as advertising efficiency, customer relationship management or product development. These measures all aim to boost marketing efficiency for corporations. Behavioural marketing, on the other hand, focuses on the demand perspective. It aims to understand the effects of marketing initiatives on customers and companies by examining customers' perceptions, thought processes, and behaviours. (Bruhn et al., 2023)

Marketing greatly contributes to the success of a venture, with its role is “of utmost importance for the success of new ventures.”(Gruber, 2004) According to Moorman, C., & Rust, R. T. (1999), marketing is most effectively understood as the function responsible for overseeing relationships between the organization and its customers, mainly through the customer-product, customer-service delivery, and customer-financial accountability connections. The efficiency of how marketing functions while maintaining these connections significantly influences financial performance, customer relationship quality, and the success of new product introductions, surpassing the effects of a broad marketing orientation across the organization. Regarding influences within an organization, marketing plays a pivotal role in shaping responsibilities. (Workman et al., 1998) Decisions related to the distribution and structure of marketing activities appear to initiate the development of marketing within organizations, forming the groundwork for further enhancements in subsequent phases. (Fürst et al., 2023)

Media have significant impacts on the marketing process. Social media platforms assist businesses in understanding consumers' needs, thus guiding the company in effectively solving marketing challenges. These tools help establish a significant brand presence by enhancing visibility and reaching more consumers, hence forming enduring consumer relationships. (Singh, 2024)

Other studies also show that media creates benign consumption envy, which can stimulate consumers' needs to satisfy and improve to eradicate such a sense of discomfort caused by envy. This is also a field that scholars and practitioners are currently delving into to fully understand the impact of marketing strategies on consumer envy. (Zheng et al., 2023)

2.2. Sustainable Development

The World Commission on Environment and Development defined the concept of sustainable development as a method to fulfill the needs of the current generations without hindering the ability of future generations to satisfy their developmental requirements. Sustainable development encompasses the advancement in various aspects, ranging from economy to environment. Scholars regard this type of development as a "development strategy", which requires proper resource management to increase long-lasting wealth and social welfare. It also highlights the significance of development, which offers an essential basis for enhancing life quality and addressing social issues. Sustainable development should respect both ecological value and social growth and maintain a balance between these factors, integrating and cooperating with inherent contradictions to foster "comprehensive and coordinated development." (Qiu et al., 2021)

Though discussion on sustainable development often concentrates on technical or environmental issues such as carbon emissions or energy use, there is a growing recognition that sustainable development also helps preserve heritage and enrich the cultural landscape. (Feeney, 2017)

Sustainable development has also become integral to project management today due to its critical role in ensuring human survival. It is widely recognized as a fundamental measure of social progress. This development merges economic growth, social inclusivity, and environmental sustainability while considering temporal and spatial constraints. Despite its significance, defining sustainable development rigorously has proven challenging since its inception. (Cerne and Jansson, 2019)

2.3 Traditional villages and traditional crafts

Traditional villages are communities formed in the early stages of history and still inhabited by the indigenous people. These villages "hold significant historical, cultural, scientific, artistic, societal, and economic significance, and therefore require protection." (Yanan et al., 2024) Such values make These villages necessitate preservation, as well as development, to maintain continuity while still protecting the heritage of the community.

However, because of unstable economic gains, incomplete appreciation of the value of villages and low participation of residents, traditional villages have faced numerous challenges in recent years, such as constructive destruction and regional regression.

According to Duan et al., 2023, traditional crafts reflect ideology and culture, and the mastery of these crafts serves as a marker of individual or community identity. While craft encompasses diverse tangible and intangible resources, it connects people and communities to a specific place, embodying various values. Viewing crafts as products allows consumers to personalize their choices, appreciate traditions through consumption, align with local values, and forge connections between users and makers. Crafts hold economic, social, aesthetic, historical, and symbolic value, closely tied to their place of origin.

However, traditional crafts and craftsmanship, as cultural heritage, face numerous challenges. Globalization and technological advancements threaten traditional practices and erode cultural diversity. Many crafts originally

served utilitarian purposes in traditional societies but struggle to find relevance in modern lifestyles. Additionally, there is a critical issue of intergenerational transmission, with younger generations often disinterested in learning traditional crafts, further endangering their survival.

To sustain traditional crafts, proactive measures are essential. Creating viable markets is crucial, with tourism offering a potential avenue for revitalization. Tourism can stimulate demand for crafts as souvenirs, as evidenced by examples in Scotland during the 1970s, where craftsmen adapted their products to meet tourist expectations. However, this transformation is not without challenges. Preserving traditional crafts is imperative as they embody significant cultural values and contribute to community identity.

3. The current situation of some traditional villages in Vietnam

3.1 Bát Tràng village

Bát Tràng is a village famous for porcelain and pottery-making. It resides on the outskirts of Hanoi, in an area that is rich in white clay, which is suitable for creating ceramic products. Most products here are handmade and embellished with traditional decorating patterns, such as traditional dragon patterns, holy beasts, or marigolds.

Not only is Bát Tràng village a place for showcasing and trading ceramics, but it has also become a famous tourist attraction in Hanoi, drawing many visitors from both within the country and abroad. With the opening of Bat Trang Museum and numerous trading markets, Bat Trang porcelain products have reached more people, both in Vietnam and overseas. Additionally, Bat Trang products help preserve numerous historical and cultural sites such as temples, pagodas, and shrines. These architectural landmarks, along with the ceramic products and the friendly, hospitable people of Bat Trang, leave a lasting impression on visitors.

3.2 Đông Hồ village

Located to the South of Bắc Ninh province, in Thuận Thành district, Đông Hồ village is a famous traditional craft village famous for its woodcut painting. Đông Hồ painting dates back to the 11th century and has since become a crucial part in celebrating the Lunar New Year. The themes of these paintings usually revolve around good luck wishes, mythical and historical figures, along with folklore and philosophical lessons.

To create a Dong Ho painting, craftsmen apply each type of natural pigment on the carved woodblock and then press it on the điệp paper - a special type of dó paper. This process is repeated until all the different pigments are applied, and then the painting is covered with rice paste to preserve its condition.

In the 21st century, technological advancement and globalization have induced numerous changes in art styles and markets. Thanks to the efforts of artisans and support from the community, Đông Hồ painting has revived and thrived in the modern age. Along with preservation programs and annual markets in December to sell Đông Hồ paintings, cultural exchange centers also attract many tourists and have played a key role in preserving and developing this traditional art form.

Dong Ho prints continue to be cherished both domestically and internationally, To help the preservation process, the government also nominates Dong Ho prints as a UNESCO World Cultural Heritage.

3.3 Vạn Phúc village

Just 10 kilometers from the center of Hanoi, Vạn Phúc village is a renowned silk-weaving village with a history spanning over a thousand years. This village is famous for being the longest-thriving silk-weaving village and the outstanding qualities that are developed through generations of skilled craftsmen.

Van Phuc silk stands out for its variety of designs and long-standing reputation, making it one of Vietnam's most esteemed silk types. Their silk products feature intricate patterns and have unparalleled qualities that are widely acclaimed by customers.

Along with improving the durability of the products, which helps its silk products adapt to the current demands, villagers also restructure their village, transforming it into a tourist attraction where visitors can fully immerse themselves into the process of silk weaving.

3.4 Cát Đằng village

Cát Đằng is a famous lacquerware village with a history of over 600 years. Located in Ý Yên District, Nam Định, the village produces various lacquered wooden items for religious and decorative purposes and has expanded to include consumer products for both domestic and export markets. The traditional craft requires significant skill and patience, often taking several months to complete each piece.

With modern machines allowing for increased production and lower costs while maintaining quality, the village is now also involved in oil lacquerware and bamboo crafts, with a significant focus on export markets.

The local government supports the industry by creating dedicated production areas, providing business loans, and promoting products. The village's economic activities contribute significantly to local income and employment, and efforts are being made to preserve and advance traditional techniques.

3.5 Non nước village

Located in Ngũ Hành Sơn district, Đà Nẵng, Non nước village is one of the most renowned traditional craft villages with a history of nearly 400 years in stone carving. Although initially started as a secondary occupation, stone carving gradually evolved into a primary industry in the village, attracting many workers and generating substantial profits.

The village is known for its diverse range of products, including religious statues, jewelry, and large art pieces. Each product shows the remarkable skills of traditional artisans in the village. The village's products are internationally exported and are well-loved by visitors.

In addition to stone carving, Non Nuoc Village is closely associated with the Marble Mountains and festivals such as the Quan The Am Festival, which attract many tourists. Non Nuoc Stone Carving Village was recognized as a National Intangible Cultural Heritage in 2014, highlighting the significance and value of this traditional craft in the cultural life of the Marble Mountains region.

4. Interview results

4.1 Results on artisans' perception of traditional crafts

Question: As a local craftsman, what is your opinion on the role of traditional crafts in society?

“Traditional craft is integral to society, in the same way that food and clothing are necessary for such society. Through its distinct aesthetics and materials, traditional crafts reflect cultural identity. (Balaram, 2011)

“Each community adapts its crafts according to its lifestyle, thus traditional crafts represent the manifestation of socio-cultural heritage. Craft not only meets fundamental human needs but also serves as a means of aesthetic expression within the community. ” (Mukherjee and Ghosh, 2020)

4.2 Results on measures to preserve traditional crafts

Question: What specific methods have people used to preserve traditional crafts within your community?

“Aside from diversifying our products to cater to modern tastes, we have implemented various strategies, such as producing promotional videos and sharing them on social media to showcase our products to the public. Additionally, we are developing websites and online exhibitions to promote traditional crafts.”

Question: What are the challenges the community faced during this process?

“The co-existence of modernity and tradition in preserving traditional crafts proves challenging. To expand beyond private spaces to gain broader acceptance and visibility in the public sphere. This requires a thorough design rethinking, and modernizing appearance and function while employing new techniques to enhance quality and durability, all without sacrificing the quintessence of the craft.” (Mukherjee and Ghosh, 2020)

4.3 Results on the impact of marketing and media on preserving traditional craft

Question: Do you think marketing and media practice contribute to the long-term sustainability of traditional crafts?

“The worldwide trend toward indigenous and organic products, along with the green movement, has renewed interest in crafts as an alternative to industrialized goods. Media and marketing contribute to this resurgence by effectively promoting the unique stories and values behind traditional crafts, fostering a greater appreciation among consumers, and encouraging sustainable practices within the marketplace.” (Mukherjee and Ghosh, 2020)

5. Conclusion

An essence of Vietnamese cultural heritage, traditional craft has proved its significance through generations, with craft villages being the core of this century-long tradition. As the age of modernization and globalization reshape consumers' behaviors, effective media campaigns and marketing strategies play integral roles in facilitating craft villages' engagement with customers.

Through real-life cases in various craft villages such as the Bat Trang village, Đông Hồ village, Vạn Phúc village, Cát Đằng village, and Non Nước village, the ties between media and marketing strategies and traditional craft villages are reflected. Craftsmanship plays a pivotal role in these villages, helping them increase in popularity and providing income for the local citizens. Handicrafts from certain villages have retained global recognition, supporting the economic activities of the region as well as promoting the cultural preservation process of the long-thriving traditional crafts.

Sustainable development in traditional craft villages is the result of efficient media and marketing tactics. The co-existence of tradition and modernity poses challenges to the development of traditional crafts. Media and marketing strategic applications balance economic viability and cultural preservation, ensuring that these heritage-rich communities thrive in the face of change.

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